

THE REFLECTION OF THE IDEA OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL EDUCATION IN THE WORKS OF ABDULLA AVLONI

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ABSTRACT: *The views of Abdullah Avloni in the field of education are closely related to the psyche, lifestyle, national values of the Uzbek people, the study of whether he served as a national school and a valuable resource is becoming a requirement of the times.*

Keywords: *education, upbringing, pedagogy, ethics, hobby, school.*

Every nation has its own spiritual image. Today, in our society, which is progressing in all aspects, raising spirituality is one of the high tasks. In the further development of our spirituality, the importance and place of historical artistic and scientific works that artistically reflect the history and spiritual image of our nation is incomparable. There are many such works in Uzbek literature. They are important in bringing the young generation to maturity. In this regard, the famous Uzbek writer Abdulla Avloni's four-part "Literature or National Poems" and "The First Teacher", "Turkish Gulistan or Morality", Textbooks such as "The Second Teacher" and "School Gulistan" are also considered to be characteristic. The ideological completeness of the perfect ideas in these works, the scientific-theoretical basis of the ideas on the educational system and concepts are proof of our above opinions. Also, the fact that Abdulla Avloni was embodied as a perfect creator of the first textbooks with his creative heritage, the concepts of education and training, ideological and artistic observations in his works were researched, and the relevance of the topic is the most important today in the work of the enlightened writer and brilliant creator Abdulla Avloni. The evidence of thoughts on the important issue of education and upbringing is visible in the case of stories, poetic scenes or metaphorical stories. On August 3, 2017, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev held a meeting with representatives of creative intellectuals of our country. At this meeting, many problems arising in the field of culture and art were revealed. At this meeting, there was talk about the large-scale work to be carried out in order to fundamentally reform the sphere of culture, mass media, literature and art, new ideas, initiatives and proposals for the education of young talents, development of our culture and literature. stated: "There is

another very important issue that will never leave the agenda for us, and I think it is necessary to pay special attention to it, and it is related to the education of our young generation, our children. 'liq. As our great grandfather Abdulla Awlani said, this issue is really a matter of life or death for us, or salvation or destruction, or happiness or disaster. In this sense, the views of Abdulla Avloni in the field of education are closely connected with the mentality, lifestyle, and national values of the Uzbek people. It is becoming a demand of the times to study the fact that the national school served as a valuable resource for raising spiritually mature youth. The works created by Abdullah Avloni for the school and the illumination of moral concepts in them are not only an artistic expression of the issue of education, but also a unique historical-pedagogical, educational It is a cultural and public monument. As we closely familiarize ourselves with Avloni's works, we once again admit that the educational, educational, ideological and philosophical pedagogic wisdoms expressed in his works still amaze us today with their vital content. It is worth noting that the principles of humanity, hard work, patriotism and ethics, which define the essence of Avloni's works, have lessons that are very instructive even for the present time. Avloni was born on July 12, 1878 in the Mergancha neighborhood of Tashkent city. The artist is a writer, a public figure and a talented pedagogue who has made significant contributions to the development of the art and literature of the Uzbek people, as well as national culture and public education. He was one of the first to turn the Uzbek theater into a professional theater, contributed to the development of the press and education. He is considered one of the prominent representatives of the Jadid movement, who carried out spiritual and educational work in Turkestan. Avloni's work was highly appreciated and he was awarded the title of "Hero of Labor" in 1925, and the title of "Educator of Uzbekistan" in 1930 for his long-term work in the promotion of Uzbek culture and literature, training of employees. Also, the writer was awarded with the order "For Great Services" on September 30, 2020 for his incomparable contribution to the creation of the national education system. Poems" and textbooks such as "The First Teacher" (1912), "Turkish Culture or Ethics" (1913), "The Second Teacher" (1915), "School Gulistan" (1917). , calls for science, school and education. At the beginning of the 20th century, there were many alphabets written for new schools. Among them, Avloni's work "The First Teacher" has its own place. Saidrasul Azizi in Avloni's writing y's work "Ustozi avul" is based on. Avloni's work "The Second Teacher" is a continuation of the book "The First Teacher". We can tentatively call the first book the alphabet, and the second book the chrestomathy. The book begins with a poem praising the school:

School makes you human.

School gives life

School grief destroys,
Study diligently, boy!
Knowledge is perfect in school,
It's good at school,
The school is a national fantasy
Study diligently, boy!

In this poem, Avloni praises the school as a way of salvation for a person, a flower of life, a force that mobilizes people towards perfection. Therefore, it is emphasized that the place of education is the school. Among Avloni's educational works, "Turkish Gulistan or Ethics" is an important moral and educational work. The work reflects on the idea of science and morality, which calls people to goodness and deters them from evil. Also, he thinks about the role of child education and says: "If a person's ego is corrupted at a young age, he grew up without education and morals, expecting good from such people is like reaching out from the ground and reaching for the stars." In his opinion, social environment, family conditions and people around children are important for the composition of moral qualities in children. In the history of Uzbek pedagogy, Avloni was defined as the first "pedagogy", that is, the science of child education. Avloni divides child education relatively into 4 sections:

1. Time of education.
2. Physical education.
3. Thought education.
4. Moral education

And he thinks about its importance. In the "Time of Education" section, it is emphasized that it is necessary to provide education from a young age, and everyone should be involved in this work: parents, teachers, the government, and others. After all, education is not a private matter, but a national social matter. "As a result, education for us is a matter of life or death, salvation or destruction, happiness or disaster," he says. The author states that the progress of every nation and the power of the state depend in many ways on the education of generations. Education starts from the birth of offspring and continues until the end of life. It consists of several stages - home, kindergarten, school and community education. Avloni understands the scope of education in a broad sense. He does not limit it to only morality. He emphasizes the need to take care of the child's health first of all. The work "Turkish Gulistan or Morality" promotes the ideas of enlightenment. Adib says about knowledge in the book: "Knowledge is the honor of the world and the honor of the hereafter." Knowledge is a very high and sacred quality for a person. Because science shows us our situation and actions like a mirror.

In short, Avloni's creative heritage is a propagator of the idea of spiritual and educational education. The ideas about education put forward in his works serve as a valuable resource for the development of our national spirituality. It is not wrong to say that the work and practical work of this great writer is a lesson for our youth today.

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